

Joint Conditional Probability and the Bound Quantum Density

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In a number of previous notes, we have argued that the bound state quantum problem may be considered in terms of a conditional probability $P(p/x)$ i.e. $\sum_p p^* p / 2m P(p/x) + V(x) = E$ with $P(p/x) = a(p) f(p,x) / W(x)$ (where $W(x)$, a normalization constant, is identical to the wavefunction). In other words, one considers a momentum distribution at x (with the different times pulled out). This momentum distribution may be thought of as being created by a stochastic potential which on average is $V(x)$. Thus, within a little region δx , in which one potential hit occurs, a particle has a joint conditional probability to move from momentum p_1 to p_2 . Because the potential is stochastic, it is not clear where in the region δx this occurs. Thus, we suggest a joint conditional probability of \sum on p_1, p_2 $f(p_1,x) f(p_2,x)$. This is equivalent to $W(x) W(x)$ the quantum density or $P(x)$. From this, one may calculate $P(p) = \sum_x P(p/x) P(x)$ leading to the idea that $f(p,x)$ is an orthonormal basis. Thus, one moves from probability to linear algebra. We suggest that the stochastic force may be given by: $-\sum_k V_k(x)$, where $-d/dx V_k(x) = -k V_k(x)$ or at least $V_k(x) = V_k(kx)$. If one considers the bound state Schrodinger equation: $\sum_p P(p/x) p^* p / 2m + V(x) W(x) = E W(x)$ then $V(x) W(x) = \sum_p V_k(x) a(p-k) f(p-k,x)$. $V_k(x)$, however, is associated with a hit of momentum $=k$, so one would expect that $V_k(x) f(p-k,x) = f(p,x)$. This together with $V_k(x) = V_k(kx)$ may lead to $V(p,x) = b(p) f(p,x)$ where $f(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$.

Quantum Bound State Density

Quantum bound state density is interesting in that it is given by $W(x) W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. In classical physics, one does not deal with a "square root" of density. Even if one considers a conditional probability $P(p/x)$ where one has a momentum distribution at x caused by a stochastic potential equal to $V(x)$ on average, one does not see the presence of a spatial density. Nevertheless, even with conditional probability, $P(x)$ (spatial density) exists and so must be determined. In a previous note, we used $P(x/p) = P(p \text{ and } x) / P(p)$ and $P(p/x) = P(p \text{ and } x) / P(x)$ together with $P(p/x) = f(p,x) a(p) / W(x)$. We argued that $P(x/p) = W(x) f(p,x) / a(p)$ and then obtained $P(x) = W(x) W(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p) a(p)$. A physical sense of the spatial density, however, seems to be missing in the above argument. If one has a single particle with a momentum distribution (at different times) at x , why should there be a spatial density? A spatial density seems to be related to kinematics in the sense that a particle spends much time in a high density area and little time in a low density area. For a point x , the conditional probability is $f(p,x) a(p) / W(x)$. Spatial density is multiplied by δx in one dimension (or dV in 3 dimensions). Thus, one is interested in a little region δx in which a particle with momentum p_1 stochastically changes to p_2 due to a potential hit. This "one" hit may occur anywhere in the δx region. Thus, in the δx region, it seems one has a joint conditional probability: $a(p_1) f(p_1,x) a(p_2) f(p_2,x)$. We have dropped the two normalization constants, thus we have relative probabilities. If one writes:

Sum $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p_1, p_2 \dots a(p_1)f(p_1,x) a(p_2)f(p_2,x) = W(x)W(x) = \text{density}(x)$ and forces $\int \text{density}(x) dx = 1$ ((1))

it seems one may have a spatial density. (One should also guarantee that $\text{density}(x)$ is positive everywhere e.g. $W^*(x)W(x)$, but $W(x)$ is real for a bound state. Thus, it seems one may have a candidate for $P(x)$, namely $W(x)W(x)$).

A New Kind of Average

It was argued that one may use conditional probabilities to calculate averages at the point x . For example, the average momentum (including the particle moving forward and backwards) at x is:

$$\left[\sum_{\text{over } p} p a(p) f(p,x) \right] / \left[\sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) f(p,x) \right]$$

And the average kinetic energy is:

$$\left[\sum_{\text{over } p} p^2/2m a(p) f(p,x) \right] / \left[\sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) f(p,x) \right] \quad \text{where } \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) f(p,x) = W(x)$$

{It is interesting to note that using conditional probabilities, one obtains a $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and a $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$, the latter being linked to kinetic energy at x . Thus, one may obtain a variance squared of $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ at each x . It is interesting to note, as an aside, that $d/dx \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is proportional to the variance squared of $p \text{ conditional}$.

$$d/dx \left[-idW(x)/dx / W(x) \right] = -i \left[(d/dx d/dx W) / W - (dW/dx) (dW/dx) / (W^*W) \right]$$

Where $\langle p^2 \rangle$ is proportional to $-d/dx d/dx W / W$.

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With the idea of a spatial density, a new average is obtained by multiplying the average at point x by the spatial density i.e.

$$\text{density}(x) \text{ KE}(x) = W(x) \sum_{\text{over } p} p^2/2m a(p) f(p,x)$$

This is an interesting average as there is only one particle. The exact average simply considers the conditional probability $P(p/x)$ when calculating the average of a function of p . The density average considers $P(p/x) P(x)$ i.e. implies that there are relative probabilities for a particle to be at one x versus another and that this gives a more complete overall picture if one does not know where the particle is.

Implications on the Conditional Probability

It seems that $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ has major implications on the conditional probability $P(p/x)= a(p) f(p,x)/ W(x)$ because:

$$P(p) = \text{Sum over } x \ P(p/x) P(x) = \text{Sum over } x \ W(x) a(p) f(p,x) \quad ((2))$$

The RHS of ((2)) should yield a function of p , thus a solution follows if $f(p,x)$ is an orthonormal basis function i.e. one has now moved into the realm of . An alternative solution might follow if $\text{Integral } dx \ f(p1,x)f(p2,x)= g(p)$ with some condition linking $p1$ and $p2$ to p . ((2)) is of the form of a joint conditional probability (with the normalization constants removed). This was earlier interpreted as a $p1$ at one point with Δx and a $p2$ at another. Thus, even if there were an equation linking $p1$ and $p2$ to p , it seems there would be no physical interpretation for such a link. Thus, we suggest that $f(p,x)$ is an orthonormal basis or:

$$\text{Integral } dx \ f(p1,x) f(p2,x) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

This implies that $f(p,x)$ is not a strictly positive function. (The idea of interference appears, but it should be noted that $p1$ and $p2$ exist at different times.)

Link to Potential

In the above scenario, we argue there is a stochastic potential with an average value of $V(x)$ i.e. $V(x)= \text{Sum over } k \ V_k(x)$ where each $V_k(x)$ gives a momentum k hit or transfer. Given that $F= dp/dt$, $dp=k$ from a k momentum hit, we suggest:

$$-d/dx V_k(x) = k V_k(x) \quad ((4))$$

One may feel ((4)) is too strong an assumption. A more general solution is to assume that $V_k(x)= V_k(kx)$ so that taking d/dx brings out a k .

The goal is to link $V_k(x)$ to $f(p,x)$ in a simple manner. Consider the bound state Schrodinger equation:

$$\text{Sum over } p \ p^*p/2m a(p) f(p,x) + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((5))$$

Given that $f(p,x)$ is an orthonormal basis function, one needs to pull the appropriate $V(x)W(x)$ terms corresponding to p . To do this, one may keep in mind that $V_k(x)$ should give a momentum hit of k to $f(p1,x)$. Thus, we suggest:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum_k b(k)a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((6))$$

Or $\nabla_k(x) f(p-k,x) = f(p,x)$ ((7)) ((4)) or $\nabla_k(x)=\nabla_k(kx)$ suggests that one has a function of momentum times position so $f(p-k,x)$ should also have this form. The former condition suggests that p's are additive i.e. assuming a power law $a \propto p^d$. There is no reason for this to grow or decline as a probability, so we suggest $d=i$.

$$\nabla_k(x)= \exp(ikx) \quad f(p,x)= \exp(ipx) \text{ as a solution.}$$

Thus, it seems one may use stochastic momentum distributions and potentials to create a momentum conditional distribution at x $P(p/x)= a(p) f(p,x) / W(x)$ where $f(p,x)$ is an orthonormal basis function. This basis function in turn may be shown to be $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the Fourier basis.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though a conditional probability $P(p/x)= a(p)f(p,x)/W(x)$ may be used in a conservation of energy equation at x: $\sum_p p^2/2m P(p/x) + V(x) = E$, a particle with momentum p_1 within Δx changes stochastically to p_2 . Thus, we suggest a stochastic joint conditional probability $a(p_1)f(p_1,x) a(p_2) f(p_2,x)$ as describing the probability within Δx if one sums over p_1 and p_2 . This is an unnormalized probability and gives $W(x)W(x)$. If one ensures that $\int W(x)W(x) dx =1$ and $W(x)W(x) \geq 0$ (i.e. use $W^*(x)W(x)$), this may be interpreted as a kind of spatial density which is equal to $P(x)$. Using $P(p)= \sum_x P(p/x)P(x)$ one may argue that $f(p,x)$ is an orthonormal basis. Considering that $V(x)= \sum_k b(k) \nabla_k(x)$ where each $b(k)$ gives a momentum hit, then $-d/dx \nabla_k(x)= k \nabla_k(x)$ is a solution or the less strong $\nabla_k(x)=\nabla_k(kx)$ may be used. Next, one may consider:

$\sum_p p^2/2m f(p,x) a(p) + V(x)W(x) = EW(x)$ and pull the $f(p,x)$ coefficients, because $f(p,x)$ is an orthonormal basis. Then, one must find the "p" component of $V(x)W(x)$. $b(k)\nabla_k(x)$ gives a k momentum hit, thus one retains:

$\sum_k b(k) \nabla_k(x) a(p-k) f(p-k,x)$, but one want the basis function $f(p,x)$ so:

$\nabla_k(x)f(p-k,x)= f(p,x)$. This, together with $-d/dx \nabla_k(x)= k \nabla_k(x)$ or the less strong $\nabla_k(x)=\nabla_k(kx)$ leads to the form: $f(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$.